

DIDACTIC TEACHING PROCESS IN PEDAGOGY AS A WHOLE SYSTEM.

Rahimberdiyeva Mahfuza Muratovna

Teacher of Kokan State Pedagogical Institute

maxfuzamuratovna@gmail.com

+99890 992-76-72

Komilova Umida, Umarova Umida

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Abstract: This article discusses the specific features of primary education didactics and gives methodical recommendations. Also, the formation of the teaching process as a whole system and its importance in the educational process are discussed.

Key words: education, elementary, didactics, concept, feature, knowledge, skill, performance, competence, approach, teaching, method.

Development of education is one of the main directions in the process of educational reforms implemented in Uzbekistan. For this purpose, it is necessary to understand the basics of primary education didactics.

Didactics is an important component of pedagogy. The word "didactics" comes from Latin and refers to the study of the theory and principles of teaching. The main categories of didactics are:

- 1) teaching;
- 2) education;
- 3) study.

The teaching category of didactics represents the organization of education on the basis of scientific and systematic laws. This category is the basis of pedagogy.

The educational category of didactics means:

- imparting knowledge;
- data transmission;
- organization of students' learning activities;
- solving problems that arise during the study;
- formation of students' creativity and independence;
- assessment of students' learning.

Several studies have been carried out on the theory and practice of didactics. In this regard, the work of Czech pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius (17th century) "The Great Didactics" is especially important. In this work, the following are justified as the main principles of didactics:

- a) childcare;
- b) patriotism;
- d) humanitarianism;
- e) tolerance.

These principles of didactics are accepted in the modern education and training process, and they are considered as pedagogical laws. As a result of this approach, humanism was accepted as an ideal idea in the world education system. According to him, the age, gender, race, nationality and social status of a person are not taken into account in education and training. In this regard, the science of pedagogy has been recognized as a humanistic art for the next 4 centuries.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, educational activities are organized strictly following the laws and principles of didactics. Therefore, the educational system of our country is included in the list of advanced developing nations. Features of primary education didactics. Didactics of primary education has its own characteristics within the pedagogical sciences of Uzbekistan.

Didactics is characterized by the joint study of meaningful and procedural aspects of education. Given the issues of reorganization and improvement of practice, didactics considers education not only as an object of learning, but as an object of scientifically based design.

The subject of general didactics is the interdependence and connection between teaching (teacher's activity) and learning (student's learning activity).

The tasks of didactics are as follows:

- description and explanation of educational processes and conditions of their implementation;
- more perfect organization of the educational process, that is, development of educational systems and technologies;
- to identify, analyze and describe the general laws specific to the educational process.

Didactics is a theoretical and at the same time normative-practical science. The scientific and theoretical task of didactics is to study the existing processes of education, the connections between its various aspects, to reveal their essence, to determine the development trends and the future.

The acquired theoretical knowledge allows to direct the educational practice, to improve education in accordance with the social requirements imposed by the society. Didactics performs a practical-normative and organizational-technological task on the basis of understanding the content of education,

determining the norms of the application of educational principles and educational methods and tools.

Knowledge accumulated by mankind in the process of social development is reflected in the concepts characteristic of a certain science. Existing scientific concepts are divided into two main groups:

1. philosophical concepts;
2. special scientific, that is, concepts specific to a specific science.

Philosophical concepts such as "general and particular", "essence and phenomenon", "contradiction", "connection" are also important for didactics. Among general-scientific concepts used in didactics, "system", "structure", "task", "element" have a special place. Didactic concepts specific to pedagogy include:

1. education - a process aimed at providing students with theoretical knowledge, forming practical skills and qualifications, developing their cognitive abilities, and educating their worldviews;

2. lesson - the main form of the educational process conducted with a certain group of students under the direct guidance of the teacher;

3. learning - the process of strengthening of behavior and activity skills, competences, improvement and enrichment of existing knowledge based on perception, study, practice and certain experience;

1. the educational process is a pedagogical process organized between the teacher and students and aimed at acquiring scientific knowledge.

2. academic subject - a resource that is taught in educational institutions and contains general or specialized knowledge bases in a specific field of science.

3. educational content - the essence of scientific knowledge determined on the basis of state educational standards and intended to be mastered in certain subjects under certain conditions.

Pedagogical process is a holistic educational process of the unity and interdependence of education and training, characterized by the joint activity, cooperation and co-creation of its subjects, full development of the individual and self-realization. helps to understand. This means that, summarizing all of the above, we can conclude the following:

The teacher should pay attention not to the individual principles of teaching, but to their system, to ensure a scientifically based choice of goals, selection, content, methods and means of organizing students' activities. favorable conditions, analysis of the process of education and upbringing.

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